

**THE INFLUENCE OF FIBRE-MATRIX INTERFACE STRENGTH
ON THE TENSILE STRENGTH AND FAILURE MODE IN UNIAXIAL CFRP**

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ABSTRACT

Intermediate modulus, PAN based carbon fibres were subjected to different levels of surface treatment, prior to the infiltration of single tows with an epoxy resin to produce simple uniaxial composites. The effect of the surface treatment was to dramatically increase the interface strength but to slightly reduce the fibre tensile strength at the higher levels of treatment. The strength of the impregnated tows was progressively reduced by the treatment and the mode of failure also changed.

KEYWORDS: Carbon fibre, surface treatment, tensile strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

This work is concerned with the mechanical behaviour of simple uniaxial composites manufactured from poly-acrylonitrile [PAN] based intermediate-modulus carbon-fibres in an anhydride-cured epoxy resin. The principal variable has been the surface treatment of the fibre prior to incorporation in the resin.

This type of carbon fibre is manufactured from the PAN precursor fibre by a three-stage thermo-chemical treatment (1). These stages are usually denoted *oxidation*, *carbonization* and *graphitization*, and the balance of strength and stiffness of the resulting carbon-fibre is largely determined by the choice of

the finish [graphitization] temperature. Higher graphitization temperatures give fibres with higher tensile modulus and lower strength. However, recent improvements in processing have resulted in the introduction of fibres which combine high modulus and high elongation to failure and, hence, very high strength. The fibre used in this study has a nominal Young's modulus of 305 GPa, a tensile strength of 5.5 GPa and an elongation to failure of 1.8%. It

is designated an *Intermediate Modulus Fibre*. The work described is part of a larger European Economic Community funded project [EURAM] concerned with the effect of the fibre-matrix interface on damage development in CFRP laminates. The effects of various levels of fibre surface treatment on the strength of the fibres and on the strength and failure mode of single resin impregnated tows of the fibre is discussed.

2. FIBRE SURFACE TREATMENT

The surface characteristics of the fibres immediately after the final heat treatment stage is such that an inadequate bond is developed at the interface with common matrix resins. This is reflected by low interlaminar shear strength and low Mode I toughness [G_{Ic} , K_{Ic}] in the composite laminates. It is, therefore, necessary to subject the fibres to a surface treatment which improves the interface strength. In this case a proprietary oxidative treatment has been applied by the fibre manufacturer. This has a number of effects; the most significant being that the surface chemistry of the fibre is changed, and in particular oxygen and nitrogen concentrations have been observed to increase. A small decrease in the specific surface area has been reported and the surface energy, as measured by wetting experiments, is raised (2). There is also the possibility that "loosely adherent" material on the original surface is removed: This is a reasonable assumption on the basis that the oxidation is known to remove material from the surface but is, however, difficult to verify the exact nature of that layer.

The fibres used in this study were all manufactured as a single batch. Sub-batches were then surface treated to various arbitrary, but proportional levels. These are designated 0, 10, 50 and 100 ST [and a small quantity from another batch at 200 ST], where "100 ST" is approximately equivalent to the standard commercial process. The treated fibres were subjected to surface analysis by X-ray photo-electron spectroscopy [XPS] and the results are shown in **fig 1**. This shows the increase in oxygen and nitrogen at the higher treatment levels. Further discussion of the significance of the chemical and morphological effects is beyond the scope of the present paper.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Single Fibre Strength Tensile tests on single fibres taken from each of the main batches were carried out by our collaborators Desaegeer and Verpoest (3). Their data is reproduced in **Table 1**. It shows that the fibre strength tends to rise slightly at the 10 and 50 levels of treatment and then to fall at the higher levels. This behaviour would support a hypothesis that initially a thin, flawed [loosely adherent?] layer is removed from the fibre, increasing its strength, whilst at higher levels of treatment the strength reduction may be attributed to an "etching" or "pitting" effect. It should also be noted that the scatter in the data, as indicated by the Weibull exponent, w , tends to be lower [higher value of w] at the intermediate levels. The reasons for this are not understood, but similar trends have been observed in similar experiments with different carbon fibres (4).

3.2 Impregnated Tow Tests The fibre was supplied as continuous tows of 12000, 4.8 μm diameter filaments. The tows used in this work had been surface treated, as described, and both sized and unsized materials were tested. The sized tows had been impregnated with approximately 1% by weight of a proprietary epoxy resin size immediately after the surface treatment. This size binds the fibres lightly together and generally makes the tow easier to handle and less prone to fraying. The impregnated tows were prepared by passing them through a small bath of resin, [a standard bisphenol-A based epoxide cured with nadic-methyl anhydride], which was heated to approximately 50°C to reduce its viscosity, and then through a PTFE die to remove excess resin and consolidate the bundle and finally the impregnated tow was led vertically upwards through a tubular oven set at 100°C, which cured the resin to beyond its gel-point, but did not fully cure it. The apparatus is shown schematically in fig 2, it allows the continuous production of the impregnated and partially cured tow at a rate of approximately 5 m/hr. Lengths of approximately 150 mm are then cut from these tows and prepared for tensile testing. This involves fitting a braided glass-fibre sheath over the gripped portions with a resin fillet and casting a pair of extensometer supports at a 50 mm gauge length, as shown in fig 3. This ensures that premature failure does not occur at the end of the gripped portion and that an extensometer may be supported without damaging the tow. The prepared test pieces are then finally cured by heating in an oven at 120°C for 3 hours followed by a postcure at 150°C for a further 3 hours.

The specimens were then tested in tension in an Instron testing machine at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min, corresponding to a strain rate of approximately $1.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$. A force/strain graph was plotted, on an X-Y recorder, from which the breaking force and the modulus were determined.

The tensile failure stress [maximum stress] was calculated on the basis of the nominal total cross sectional area of the fibre in the tow - that is 12 000 fibres each 4.8 μm in diameter. The resin is considered not to contribute to the tensile strength. The results quoted are, thus, not influenced by small differences in fibre fraction. This was measured and found to average approximately 0.55 for all the batches tested.

At the completion of each test the fragments of the bundle were collected for visual and microscopic examination. It should be noted, however, that when these very strong materials fail, there is an almost explosive release of elastic strain energy, which often results in considerable consequential damage [ie post-failure]. Many fragments are formed and scattered. It is, therefore, very difficult to identify the location of the primary failure site.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Single Fibre Tests A total of 8 - 10 tests were carried out on unsized fibres, at each of four gauge lengths, for each of the four surface treatments. These results are summarised in Table 1. The data must be treated with caution, on account of the small sample size, but a general trend

of higher strength at shorter gauge lengths is apparent. Also in general the strengths at the 10 and 50 ST levels tend to be higher as is the scatter at the 100 ST level.

TABLE 1
SINGLE CARBON FIBRE TENSILE TEST DATA

Surface Treatment Level	Gauge Length [mm]	Mean Tensile Strength [GPa]	Weibull Exponent w	Characteristic Strength α [GPa]
0	80	4.26	9.0	7.33
	30	5.34	17.5	6.69
	10	5.83	12.0	7.37
	5	6.72	6.9	9.06
10	80	4.53	9.4	7.62
	30	5.29	7.9	8.68
	10	5.96	14.8	7.19
	5	6.40	8.7	8.12
50	80	4.25	10.3	6.84
	30	4.36	15.1	5.66
	10	5.49	4.6	9.88
	5	5.74	7.0	7.71
100	80	4.32	7.7	8.13
	30	4.58	8.7	7.21
	10	5.63	6.0	8.92
	5	6.42	7.9	8.43

Results from Desaegeer & Verpoest (3)

The strength at the 100 ST level, however, is relatively high and does not correlate with the results from the bundle tests. The parameter α is the strength at a gauge length of 1 mm calculated according to the Weibull weak link scaling hypothesis [$\sigma_0 = \alpha \times L^{-1/w}$]. This parameter is very consistent in each set and a further comparison of the values of w and α for the four surface treatments is given in [Table 2], this data, derived from a plot of $\ln \sigma_0$ vs. $\ln L$ is less sensitive to the extreme values of each set; it indicates reduced scatter at the 10 and 50 ST levels and a general reduction in strength with surface treatment, although the 100 ST values remain anomalous. It should be noted that if the scatter is abnormally high, ie w low, an anomalously high estimate of α will result.

TABLE 2
COMPARISON OF WEIBULL EXPONENT AND CHARACTERISTIC STRENGTH FOR SINGLE CARBON FIBRES AT 4 SURFACE TREATMENT LEVELS

ST	0	10	50	100
w	6.50	8.01	8.29	6.59
α	9.20	8.42	7.41	8.65

Desaegeer and Verpoest (3) have estimated the interface strength using the single embedded fibre fragmentation test (5). This used a different epoxy resin formulation but indicates a progressive increase in interface strength with the surface treatment as shown in Table 3. The fragment length is inversely related to the interface strength.

TABLE 3
SINGLE EMBEDDED FIBRE FRAGMENTATION TEST
MEAN SEGMENT LENGTHS AT 10% APPLIED STRAIN

ST	0	10	50	100
SL[μm]	312	281	160	81

4.2 Impregnated Bundle Tests A total of between 91 and 140 *successful* tensile tests were conducted on batches of un-sized and sized impregnated tow at each of the four surface treatment levels - a total of 912 individual tests. A *successful* test is defined as one in which the bundle failed within the gauge portion and neither within the grips nor at the junction of the gauge portion and the grip fillet.

TABLE 4
IMPREGNATED CARBON FIBRE TOW TENSILE TEST DATA

Surface Treatment Level	Unsize Fibres		Sized Fibres	
	Tensile Strength σ_o [GPa]	Weibull Exponent w	Tensile Strength σ_o [GPa]	Weibull Exponent w
0	5.7	12	5.7	15
10	5.7	28	5.8	31
50	5.2	9.2	5.4	18
100	5.0	14	4.7	17

The results are summarised in Table 4. Cumulative distribution plots of probability of failure, P_f , versus tensile strength are shown in **fig 4**. This shows an increase in strength at the 10 ST level, notably the elimination of the lower "tail" of the distribution, which reduces the scatter. The strength falls significantly at the 50 and 100 ST levels and the tail reappears. A Weibull plot of the ST 10 data, **fig 5**, is very linear, indicating an excellent fit to the Weibull distribution. Results from another batch of material tested at a 200 mm gauge length are shown in **fig 6**, this indicates that the strength is further reduced at the 200 ST level. A very clear trend emerges which is summarised in **figs 7 and 8**. There is little change in strength, possibly a slight rise, at the 10 ST level but thereafter at the higher treatment levels there is a definite downward trend. A further interesting feature [**fig 8**] is the sharp increase in the Weibull exponent, w , at the 10 ST level.

It was also observed that when the bundles with the 0 ST fibres failed, there was extensive splitting of the bundle and many small fragments were formed. At the 10, 50 and 100 ST levels there was much less splitting and the 100 ST material almost always failed by a single *brittle* transverse fracture. In general the sized materials fragmented to the greater extent.

5. DISCUSSION

The effects of the surface treatment are that the surface chemistry of the

fibre is changed and the interface strength of the fibre in an epoxy resin is considerably enhanced. There is some indication that the strength of the fibre may be slightly enhanced at the 10 ST level and that it is weakened at higher levels. It is difficult, however, to draw firm conclusions from the small samples tested. But similar trends have been observed with another carbon fibre treated and tested in a similar manner (4). In this case there is also a firmer indication of decreased scatter at intermediate treatment levels.

The strength of the impregnated bundles is clearly shown to decrease at ST levels of 50 and above. The data here is much more reliable as many more duplicate tests were carried out and in any case the variability of *bundles* is much less than that of single fibres. Here again there is strong evidence of reduced scatter at the 10 ST level [fig 8]. The bundles are generally stronger than fibres of equivalent gauge length [50 mm] and this may be attributed to the need for the formation of critical groups of failed fibres [*i-plets* in Batdorf's terminology (6)] to initiate bundle failure. It might be expected that a higher interface strength, by reducing the load transfer length [*ineffective length*] would tend to **increase** the bundle strength but, in fact, the opposite is observed. One possible reason is that the *true* fibre strength may be reduced to a greater extent than is indicated by the single fibre tensile tests.

An alternative explanation may lie in the mode of failure: At the lower levels of surface treatment extensive splitting is observed. This is a feature of the tensile failure of uniaxial composites of low interface strength. It has been proposed (7) that as a critical *i-plet* develops, shear stresses at the "crack" tip lead to splitting parallel to the fibres. This effectively halts the progress of the crack and prevents it from continuing across the section. Further critical *i-plets* will need to form, with further splitting, until the whole section is sufficiently weakened by an accumulation of micro-cracks. The failure process appears to be virtually instantaneous so that it is difficult to observe how much of the splitting occurs prior to failure and how much is the result of the explosive release of energy consequent to the failure.

Whilst not providing a firm conclusion this work serves to illustrate that even a fibre dominated property such as tensile failure of a uniaxial composite is significantly affected by the nature of the interface [and possibly also the matrix].

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FIGURE 1. Oxygen and nitrogen concentrations on surface treated carbon fibres - determined by XPS.

FIGURE 2. Apparatus for the production of partially cured, single carbon fibre tows impregnated with an epoxy resin.

FIGURE 3. Impregnated tow test piece.

FIGURE 4. Cumulative distribution plots for the 4 sets of sized fibre impregnated tow tensile tests. The 10 ST curve is slightly displaced towards higher strength and the lower "tail" is eliminated - resulting in less scatter. At the higher ST levels the curves are displaced downwards relative to the 0 ST.

FIGURE 5. The test data for the 10 ST sized fibre tows is plotted on Weibull axes. The slope of the best fit straight line gives the Weibull exponent w and the intercept at $\ln.\ln \{1/(1-P_f)\} = 0$ gives the characteristic stress σ_0 .

FIGURE 6. Tensile strength of impregnated tows from another batch of similar carbon fibre, showing that the decrease in strength continues up to the 200 ST level of surface treatment.

FIGURE 7. Characteristic strength [σ_0] vs. surface treatment level for the main batch of impregnated carbon fibre tows.

FIGURE 8. The value of the Weibull exponent, w [shape parameter] for the tows of fig 7. is plotted vs. surface treatment level. Note the increase at the 10 ST level indicating reduced scatter - cf also fig 4.